

The importance of nature for tourists: evidence from multiple perspectives using social media data.

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Summary

Nature-based tourism is a rapidly growing subsector of the global tourism industry, but understanding how important ‘nature’ is for tourists may be challenging with traditional data sources. This study examines the role of nature for tourists using social media data. The place-based, content-based and user-based analyses demonstrate the overall importance of nature for tourists, while revealing differing patterns across the islands and among tourists from different regions. The study underscores the importance of nature in tourism and demonstrates the potential of social media data for informing tourism and conservation planning.

KEYWORDS: social media data, Canary Islands, protected area management,

1. Introduction

The travel and tourism sector is one of the largest and fastest growing global industries, corresponding to an estimated 10 % of global GDP in 2019 (WTTC, 2022). Nature-based tourism is a rapidly growing subsector of the international tourism industry, with increasing interest trends being reported globally (Waldron *et al.*, 2020) as well as in established beach tourism destinations such as the Canary Islands (Hästbacka *et al.*, 2024). While the general understanding of nature as an attractor for tourism is well known, there is much less understanding on the magnitude or spatial distribution. Such information is difficult to derive using traditional data sources, but social media data may offer insights. Here, we attempt to estimate the importance of ‘nature’ for tourists visiting the Canary Islands using social media data from the photo-sharing platform Flickr as an information source. We examine the topic through three approaches (Toivonen *et al.*, 2019):

- (1) Place-based approach: What share of all content posted to Flickr is posted from ‘nature’?
- (2) Content-based approach: What share of visual content relate to nature and what topics emerge?
- (3) User-based approach: Are there differences between user groups based on their country of origin?

2. Study area

The Canary Islands is an autonomous region (*Comunidad autónoma*) of Spain, and tourism forms the backbone of the local economy. While tourism in the region relies on the 3S (Sun, Sand and Sea) model, it is also a site of high endemic biodiversity and rich geodiversity. The archipelago’s 147 protected areas are popular and relatively accessible attractions for tourists, but only four of them currently collect systematic visitor information.

3. Data

We downloaded 723 012 geotagged Flickr posts (394 295 with images) posted between 2004 and 2023,

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and 89 733 Instagram posts posted between 2015 and 2016.

We used both protected area (UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, 2023) and land cover classification data (European Environment Agency, 2019) to produce a classification with four categories of ‘nature’: Protected areas, other areas of high biodiversity value, non-protected nature, and other areas.

4. Place-based analysis and results

Interpreting social media photographs as landscape values (Van Zanten *et al.*, 2016), we analysed the distribution of posts into the different nature categories by Island. The place-based analysis showed that 31.7 % of Flickr photos were taken in nature, 24.3 % in protected areas and 7.4 % in natural areas outside protection area. The proportion of nature posts varied considerably between the different Islands, while the proportion of land classified as nature remained more constant.

5. Content-based analysis and results

We applied a semantic clustering approach (Väisänen *et al.*, 2021) with a pre-trained ResNet101 model (Xie *et al.*, 2016) in combination with UMAP (McInnes *et al.*, 2018) and HDBSCAN (McInnes, Healy and Astels, 2017) to automatically cluster the photographs based on the semantic similarity of their visual contents. We then named the clusters by visually inspecting a 2.5% sample of each cluster. To assess the accuracy of the naming, we took a separate 2.5 % sample of each cluster.

The pipeline produced 31 individual clusters, which contained 65.6 % of all content. 25.9 % of Flickr photos were classified into the nature-related clusters. Photos of humans was the largest individual cluster for all user groups and across land uses. Different nature-related contents also emerged as important, with many of the largest clusters forming around specific landscape types or animals. By analysing the distribution of different clusters spatially, we found that an important proportion of nature-related contents had been posted outside of areas classified spatially as nature (**Figure 1**). For instance, most photos of animals were taken in non-natural areas, with less photos having been taken in natural settings.

Figure 1 Output of the semantic clustering pipeline, with the points representing individual photos. photos from nature are coloured green; the rest are coloured according to their land use category. Noise is not shown.

6. User-based analysis and results

To understand variation between user groups, we calculated four user-level metrics to describe individual users' spatial behaviour: proportion of posts from nature, proportion of posts from PAs, number of visited PAs, and the share of clustered content in nature-related clusters. We then used one-way ANOVAs to compare the different groups.

61.8% of all Flickr users had posted at least once from nature, and 46.8 % from a PA. On average, 25.9 % of the users' clustered content belonged to the nature clusters. We observed significant differences in nature visitation patterns between visitors from different countries. Overall, our results suggest that a majority of visitors to the Canary Islands engage in nature-based recreation during their visit. However, we found the general interest in visiting nature or posting about nature-related topics to be higher among visitors from Central and Southern European countries and lower for visitors from Northern Europe.

7. Validation

To validate the results of the empirical analyses, we interviewed local experts familiar with tourism in the Canary Islands. We also compared the results against official visitor survey statistics, showing that the inter-group differences in posting patterns were largely reflected by observed differences in different tourist groups' eagerness to participate in nature-related activities.

8. Thoughts for the future

Our results confirm that nature plays an important role in the Canary Islands, a destination where beach and sun are usually considered as the main attractions. As tourism in general and nature-based tourism continue to grow, visitation pressures to natural areas are likely to increase. This emphasizes the need of further knowledge of visitor preferences and interests, as well as the importance of well-planned conservation actions. Our findings demonstrate that social media data can provide insights about people's use of space and interactions with nature in a spatially explicit way. At the same time, we encourage simultaneously considering different approaches to social media data, as they provide complementary perspectives into the issues of interest.

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